

VALERIANA OFFICINALIS L. – MAIN RAW MATERIAL FOR PRODUCING DRUGS FOR THE TREATMENT OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

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Relevance. The use of valerian has a long history in folk medicine. It was mentioned in written sources as early as the 2nd century as a sleep aid and sedative. Valerian preparations were recommended by Galen for insomnia, and in the 16th century, they were used to treat nervousness, palpitations, and headaches. Beginning in the mid-20th century, valerian tincture began to be used for stressful situations.

Purpose of the study. The purpose of our research is study of the medical use of the main raw materials of valerian in medicinal practice, namely for the relief of pain in the heart and the treatment of cardiovascular diseases .

Materials and Methods. For the study, we used the following primary sources: Avicenna's textbook "The Canon of Medicine," methodological manuals and a textbook on herbal medicine, an atlas of medicinal plants of Uzbekistan, a textbook on clinical pharmacology, and articles on the anatomical and morphological structure of valerian, its distribution, and the collection of medicinal plant materials. Additional information was obtained from internet resources, online encyclopedias, and electronic libraries.

Results. Valerian officinalis, a perennial herbaceous plant, reaches a height of 1-1.5 meters. It grows in the Caucasus, Europe, the Far East, and Siberia, and is also cultivated in Central Asia. Valerian's medicinal raw material is the roots and rhizomes, harvested in early spring (when the leaves are unfurling) or late fall (when the leaves are drying). After cleaning, washing, and drying, the raw material is ready for use. Valerian root and rhizome contain essential oil, isovaleric acid, and other chemical compounds. Valerian's action is based on the complex of these organic substances. Its effects are diverse. For example, it has a calming and anti-anginal effect on the central nervous system. It also stimulates cardiac activity, relieves smooth muscle spasms (has an antispasmodic effect), stimulates bile secretion from the liver, and enhances gastric secretion. The sedative effect of valerian is associated with decreased CNS excitability and enhanced inhibition. It also has an inhibitory effect on the reticular formation. As a result, valerian helps improve sleep and reduce stimulant-induced palpitations. It also dilates blood vessels and has a significant hypotensive effect. Herbal remedies made from the roots of this plant, as well as galenic preparations, are recommended for the treatment of nervous disorders, agitation, insanity, and mood disorders such as neuroses, nervous exhaustion, autonomic neuropathy, and others, as well as for the treatment of insomnia and migraines. Valerian is particularly useful in the treatment of cardiovascular neurosis, angina, and high blood pressure. Preparations based on valerian have an antagonist effect against brucine and reduce the stimulating effects of caffeine.

Conclusions. The results presented in the review confirm the value and availability of valerian as a medicinal plant material for use in various phytotherapeutic formulations for the correction of a variety of pathological conditions and the treatment of numerous ailments.